

LLM Assisted Online Root-Causing of Misconfiguration Diagnosis in Enterprise Computing Systems

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Abstract—Misconfigurations in Enterprise systems are ubiquitous due to the large number of configuration parameters with poorly understood functionality and interdependencies between them. Diagnosing misconfigurations online starting with an, often vague, user complaint is a difficult problem. In our prior and ongoing work we have developed an effective method to root-cause the problem in large enterprise systems. These diagnosis procedures start with an initial category of the problem experienced, which can be considered as a “trouble-ticket”. In this paper we explore how the emerging large language models (LLMs) can be used to build a chatbot that converses with the user to gather all relevant information from the user via a multi-step dialog and then builds the trouble ticket. We demonstrate this task oriented dialog (ToD) capability in two diagnosis contexts: (a) microservices and service mesh related faults, and (b) enterprise network faults. In order to explore the chatbot capabilities more broadly, we use the fine-tuning for (a) and instruction tuning for (b). We show that in both cases, the chatbot can hold a meaningful dialog and generate a trouble ticket successfully.

I. INTRODUCTION

Misconfigurations in Enterprise systems have become a ubiquitous source of operational issues and are routinely exploited by attackers to gain access or disrupt systems. The primary cause of misconfigurations is the large number of configuration parameters with poorly understood functionality and interdependencies between them. The recent DevOps practices, particularly Continuous Integration/Continuous Development (CI/CD), substantially increase the frequency of changes to the software and its configuration [1]. Same or similar faulty configuration pushed out to many nodes (servers, routers, etc.) in a large distributed enterprise could cause widespread outages. On the other hand, site specific configurations along with cross-site visibility limitations could make the root causing of the problem quite difficult [2, 3].

In a production system, misconfiguration diagnosis often starts as a result of user complaint. The user complaint is usually vague and cannot be directly used to create a trouble ticket for diagnosis. Traditionally, the user would have a conversation with the administrator who might ask the user to better describe the problem or conduct some simple checks before preparing a trouble ticket. The next step is to conduct a diagnosis procedure to root-cause the problem down to the specific configuration variables (CVs) that may be set incorrectly. It is highly desirable to do the latter using standard

set of tests, which also means that in some situations the tests are not discriminative enough to pinpoint precise CVs.

In our prior work [4], we have developed a diagnosis procedure using standard tests that starts with the trouble ticket indicating potential problem with one or more services. The method systematically selects the next test based on results of the prior test until either we find the root cause of the problem or exhaust the tests to be conducted. We have also developed a similar mechanism for microservices environment which uses service-mesh to easily control the number of active instances of microservices based on the demand. The microservices paradigm is quite different from the traditional services environment, and results in different sets of symptoms and tests needed to diagnose problem. In this paper, we demonstrate two different chatbot designs for these two very different environments in order to converse with the user and prepare an appropriate trouble ticket. The chatbot is based on the emerging large language models (LLMs) which not only allows the chatbot to have a natural language conversation with the user but also support substantial level of generalizability. That is, the chatbot does not operate by using phrases from a database and does not need to be trained with huge number of pairs of questions and responses. Instead, a rather limited training dataset can enable the chatbot to handle a much wider range of utterances from the user.

Fig. 1: Illustration of Chatbot in Diagnosis

Fig. 1 shows the overall system that we envision. Once the trouble ticket is prepared based on the chatbot output, we use it with any type diagnosis algorithm, although there is a strong dependency in terms of the domain, i.e., the dialog with chatbot, trouble ticket and the diagnosis algorithm all need to be specialized for the system of interest, its entities, and fault types. The diagnosis algorithms that we have developed are specialized to their respective domains (microservices and enterprise network respectively); and in the latter case we have found that they work better than the LLM based diagnosis methods.

¹Equal Contribution. This research was supported by NSF grant CNS-2011252

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II explores fault diagnosis in microservices environments, highlighting the chatbot’s role in troubleshooting service mesh failures. Section II-B presents the evaluation methodology, experimental setup, and classification accuracy results of the microservices chatbot. Section III discusses the challenges of diagnosing enterprise network misconfigurations and introduces the ConfExp framework. Section III-B details the chatbot’s design, including its language model, instruction tuning, and response optimization techniques, and evaluation of its classification accuracy. Finally, Section IV concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

II. DIAGNOSING MICROSERVICE MISCONFIGURATIONS

Microservices architectures have become fundamental in designing scalable and modular applications. However, their distributed nature introduces inherent complexities in fault detection, diagnosis, and resolution. Figure 3 shows an example microservices application that has a complex acyclic graph structure. The most common failure modes in microservices environments include network disruptions, service-level failures, data integrity violations, and access control issues.

A service mesh functions as an intermediary layer that governs service-to-service communication, providing essential capabilities such as traffic management, security enforcement, observability, and fault injection (Figure 2). The service mesh plays a crucial role by controlling service request routing, enforcing authentication and encryption policies, collecting distributed traces and logs, and simulating failure scenarios to assess system resilience. By continuously monitoring system performance, the service mesh enables proactive anomaly detection. For example, if it detects a surge in latency for the file upload service, it generates an alert. This fault is classified as a slow service (SS) and requires a Load Test followed by horizontal scaling or code optimization as a remediation strategy. It must be noted that the chatbot does not directly query the service mesh for logs or performance metrics. Instead, the service mesh continuously monitors system performance and detects anomalies independently. When an issue such as increased latency is identified, the service mesh generates alerts, which can then be leveraged by automated fault diagnosis mechanisms, including the chatbot, to determine remediation steps.

Network-related faults typically manifest as unreachable networks (UN), where communication failures prevent inter-service connectivity, or slow networks (SN), characterized by excessive latency or bandwidth constraints. Service-layer

Fig. 2: Service Mesh Architecture

TABLE I: Reported Symptoms and Fault Classes

Code	Fault Type	Symptoms Leading to User Report
UN	Unreachable Network	Unable to load the application or parts of it.
SN	Slow Network	Experiences delays in loading content.
US	Unreachable Service	Specific features not working with errors/ timeouts.
SS	Slow Service	Certain actions taking longer than usual to complete.
DE	Data Error	Incorrect/inconsistent data displayed within the application.
DC	Data Corruption	Errors during data processing, or data loss.
UA	Unauthorized Access	Access denied when using previously accessible feature/data.
BA	Blocked Access	Unable to access parts of the application due to restrictions.

faults include unreachable services (US), in which a microservice becomes non-responsive due to failures or crashes, and slow services (SS), where performance degradation arises due to high computational loads or inefficiencies. Data-related faults involve data errors (DE), resulting from inconsistent, incomplete, or malformed data, as well as data corruption (DC), which can occur during transmission, processing, or storage. Access-related faults include unauthorized access (UA), where authentication or authorization policies block legitimate requests, and blocked access (BA), which arises due to misconfigured security policies or permission restrictions. All the codes are defined in Table I.

Diagnosing faults in microservices is inherently challenging due to the dynamic interactions between services, the ambiguity of user-reported issues, and the necessity for scalable fault resolution strategies. Traditional manual fault detection approaches are inefficient in large-scale distributed systems, making automation a necessity. To address these challenges, an automated fault diagnosis algorithm systematically identifies and classifies faults, expediting root cause analysis and remediation.

Our existing fault diagnosis algorithm systematically detects, categorizes, and localizes faults by using user-reported symptoms. The algorithm follows a structured multi-step process.

First, it acquires reported fault type as input from the user manually. Then it determines the set of microservices to perform the diagnosis on. Next, it dynamically selects relevant diagnostic tests based on observed symptoms. Each fault and test is characterized by a set of numerical features, capturing the relevance to each other. For example, for a timeout fault, doing a DNS check first is more relevant than doing database configuration checks. By determining the tests to be executed for a particular reported error, the algorithm dynamically adapts its diagnostic workflow to find out the misconfigurations relevant to each of those tests.

The automation of fault diagnosis and reporting in microservices architectures offers several advantages. First, it significantly reduces mean time to detect (MTTD) and mean time to resolve (MTTR), leading to faster fault resolution. Second, it improves scalability by supporting large-scale microservices deployments with minimal human intervention. Third, by

Model	Parameters	Architecture	Strengths	Weaknesses
Mistral-7B	7B	Decoder	Handles ambiguity, dynamic follow-ups	Higher latency, larger memory use
BERT-Base	110M	Encoder	Faster inference, lower compute costs	Struggles with vague inputs

TABLE II: Comparison of Mistral-7B and BERT-Base in terms of architecture, strengths, and weaknesses.

types of inputs, including both well-defined issues (e.g., "App won't open at all") and vague user complaints (e.g., "Things don't work anymore"). As shown in Table III, we compare the model predictions with the ground truth and gained insights into each model's ability to correctly classify and interpret user problems.

One of the most striking findings from the ground truth comparison is that Mistral-7B aligns with the ground truth more consistently than BERT, especially for ambiguous inputs (IV.). This is evident in its higher accuracy and ambiguity success rate, as seen in the quantitative performance metrics. Mistral-7B exhibits fewer misclassifications, meaning it is better at correctly identifying issues based on the user input. For structured inputs with clear descriptions (such as "IP address blocked" or "Getting 403 errors"), both models perform relatively well, indicating that even BERT can handle straightforward classification tasks with a reasonable degree of success. However, when the input becomes vague or context-dependent, BERT struggles significantly. Cases such as "Numbers don't add up" or "Where's my data?" demonstrate how BERT often assigns an incorrect category of fault. This suggests that BERT lacks the deeper contextual reasoning required to interpret user intent when the problem statement is unclear.

Another notable observation is that Mistral-7B outperforms BERT in dynamic problem-solving scenarios, such as handling follow-up clarifications. While BERT-Base tends to misinterpret ambiguous queries or assign them incorrectly, Mistral-7B demonstrates a better grasp of context, leading to improved classification accuracy in real-world scenarios where user inputs are often incomplete or imprecise. These findings suggest that Mistral-7B is better suited for applications requiring high accuracy and robust contextual understanding, such as customer support automation, troubleshooting systems, and AI-driven assistance platforms. On the other hand, BERT may be preferable in scenarios where speed and low computational cost are prioritized over deep contextual comprehension.

Input	Mistral-7B	BERT	Ground Truth
App won't open at all	UN	UN	UN
Loading takes forever	SN	SN	SN
Search not working	US	SN	US
Wrong prices shown	DE	DE	DE
Lost progress after crash	DC	DC	DC
Getting 403 errors	UA	UA	UA
IP address blocked	BA	BA	BA
Numbers don't add up	DE	DC	DE

TABLE III: Comparison of Mistral-7B, BERT, and Ground Truth on Non-Ambiguous Inputs

In our findings demonstrated in Table V., we see that that Mistral-7B has a significantly higher accuracy than BERT, outperforming it by 16.1% on the test set. This suggests

Vague Input	Mistral-7B	BERT	Ground Truth
"Things don't work anymore"	UN	UN	UN
"Everything's messed up"	UN	DC	UN
"Can't do anything"	SN	BA	UN
"It's all wrong"	DE	DE	DE
"Stuff disappeared"	DC	DE	DC
"Won't let me in"	UA	UA	UA
"Blocked for no reason"	BA	BA	BA
"Takes ages to do anything"	SN	SN	SN
"Numbers look funny"	DE	DC	DE
"Where's my data?"	DC	DE	DC

TABLE IV: Comparison of Mistral-7B, BERT, and Ground Truth on Ambiguous Inputs

that Mistral-7B excels in tasks requiring deeper contextual understanding and ambiguity resolution. However, this improvement comes with a trade-off in latency. BERT is twice as fast in terms of inference time, making it more efficient for tasks where speed is a priority. Despite this, Mistral-7B's generative capabilities justify the higher computational cost, especially in applications demanding nuanced language comprehension. One of the key advantages of Mistral-7B is its superior handling of ambiguous inputs. It achieves an 89% success rate when dealing with vague queries, compared to BERT's 58%. This makes Mistral-7B particularly well-suited for real-world scenarios where user inputs may be unclear or context-dependent. When the initial classification yields low confidence, the model generates targeted follow-up questions (e.g., "Is the slowness consistent across all app features or specific actions?") to disambiguate the context. User responses are iteratively fed back into the model for reclassification. If ambiguity persists, the chatbot asks questions pertaining to broad diagnostic faults (e.g. API ping tests) and combines results with conversational context to finalize fault classification.

Model	State	Accuracy	Latency	Ambiguity Success
Mistral-7B	Pre-trained	65.2 %	34ms	61 %
	Fine-tuned	92.3 %	40ms	89 %
BERT	Pre-trained	48.5 %	20ms	49 %
	Fine-tuned	76.2 %	20ms	58 %

TABLE V: Performance Comparison of Mistral-7B and BERT

III. DIAGNOSING ENTERPRISE NETWORK MISCONFIGURATIONS

Enterprise IT environments are composed of complex, interdependent software and infrastructure components, making them highly susceptible to misconfiguration errors. Unlike hardware failures, which often produce explicit error states, misconfigurations introduce subtle, hard-to-detect inconsistencies that may degrade performance, cause intermittent failures, or expose security vulnerabilities. These errors arise due to inconsistencies in access control policies, incorrect network

configurations, service parameter mismatches, or improperly applied updates.

Misconfigurations occur when system settings deviate from intended configurations due to human errors, software updates, conflicting policies, or undocumented system dependencies. The most common categories of enterprise misconfigurations include authentication and access control errors, network configuration issues, service-specific parameter misconfigurations, and state inconsistencies across systems. Each of these issues can disrupt critical enterprise services, leading to accessibility failures, degraded performance, or security vulnerabilities. Notably, misconfigurations account for 80% of security exposures [5]. Additionally, cloud misconfigurations contribute to up to 65% of cloud security incidents, making them a prime target for attackers [6]. These statistics highlight the critical need for effective configuration management solutions. These statistics underscore the critical need for effective configuration management solutions.

A. Enterprise Network Characteristics, Faults, and Diagnosis

Fig. 5: Network topology used in the ConfExp.

We have designed a comprehensive mechanism called ConfExp to diagnose a variety of enterprise network misconfiguration scenarios. Here we provide a brief overview – the details may be found in [4]. As shown in Fig. 5, ConfExp models a realistic enterprise IT infrastructure, consisting of routers, DNS servers, and application servers. The network consists of a number of subnets, each of which is assumed to have a local management console (LMC) that monitors and displays failures in various services and nodes. Typically LMC sits on a management network that may be physically or logically separate from the main network and has capabilities to restart failed devices and services. In addition, we also assume a virtual global management console (GMC), which can be thought of as an aggregation of information from all the LMCs so that all status information is available centrally. ConfExp monitors for misconfigurations in firewall rules, DNS records, routing table entries, database reachability, and application/web server issues. The tests used are standard tests that are commonly available (e.g., ping, traceroute, etc.) and the key issue is to intelligently decide what test to conduct next based on the symptoms and results of prior tests.

The diagnosis process follows an iterative, confidence-based approach that systematically isolates misconfigurations. It begins by identifying potentially affected services based on user complaints or automated alerts. Each CV associated with the suspected service is assigned a *confidence level* ranging from -1 to 1, where negative values indicate possible misconfigurations, and positive values suggest correctness. The system then selects the most informative test dynamically, prioritizing those with higher diagnostic relevance. At each step, the system executes the selected test and updates the confidence levels of related CVs. If a test passes, confidence in the associated CVs increases, while a failure reduces their confidence. Once a CV’s confidence drops below a predefined threshold, it is flagged as a likely root cause. The diagnosis continues until either all tests are exhausted or a conclusive misconfiguration is identified.

A distinguishing feature of ConfExp is its ability to coordinate across multiple network locations. The GMC collects reports from different LMCs, enabling cross-site fault correlation. If a service is accessible in one location but unreachable in another, the system determines whether the issue is network-related (e.g., firewall or routing misconfigurations) or service-specific (e.g., access control or database failures). Experimental results show that ConfExp significantly improves fault diagnosis compared to manual expert troubleshooting. For example, for firewall misconfigurations, the system accurately detects blocked traffic within four test steps, reducing detection time to under 15 seconds. Similarly, for routing table misconfigurations, ConfExp pinpoints errors efficiently by leveraging traceroute analysis and eliminating unnecessary tests. The diagnosis typically requires five tests, including name resolution, ping, traceroute, routing table inspection, and neighbor router checks. The entire process is completed in approximately 15–20 seconds, with traceroute being the most time-consuming step.

B. Chatbot Design for Creating Trouble Ticket

When a user encounters an issue, they describe their problem in natural language, and the chatbot engages in an iterative conversation to refine and structure the collected information. This structured approach allows the chatbot to extract the most relevant symptoms without overwhelming the user with unnecessary queries. The chatbot starts by classifying the issue into broad failure domains such as networking, database, or application-related failures. Based on this classification, it dynamically selects follow-up questions that maximize information gain.

For example, if a user reports that they cannot access a web application, the chatbot may ask targeted questions such as whether other network services are accessible, if login attempts were successful from different devices, and whether an error message was displayed. Rather than suggesting predefined troubleshooting steps, the chatbot tailors its questioning strategy based on the conversation’s progression, ensuring that it gathers all relevant details before symptom extraction.

The chatbot employs a decoder-only transformer architecture that generates responses autoregressively. The model architecture consists of multi-head self-attention (MHSA) for contextual representation learning, feedforward layers (FFN) for hierarchical reasoning, and rotary positional embeddings (RoPE) for preserving sentence order dependencies.

At each decoding step, the model predicts tokens sequentially based on prior context and structured instructions:

$$P(y_t|y_{1:t-1}, X, I) = \text{softmax}(W_o \cdot \text{Transformer}(X, y_{1:t-1})) \quad (1)$$

where X represents the user input and prior conversation history, I denotes the structured instruction-tuned prompt, W_o is the output projection matrix, and y_t is the predicted token at timestep t . To ensure controlled response generation, temperature scaling ($T = 0.7$) is applied to balance coherence and diversity, while top-p sampling ($p = 0.9$) helps prioritize the most contextually relevant tokens.

This chatbot implementation also uses Mistral-7B-Instruct [7]. The chatbot applies instruction tuning in three key areas. First, it employs prompt engineering with domain-specific constraints, ensuring that generated questions follow structured diagnostic logic. Second, dynamic response optimization via contextual reweighting allows the chatbot to refine its questioning strategy based on prior user responses. Finally, the chatbot leverages instruction tuning for knowledge injection in enterprise troubleshooting, enabling it to adapt to a variety of system failures.

Each user input is transformed into a structured prompt to ensure logical and domain-specific questioning: Prompt = $I + C + H + U$, where I is the instruction template (e.g., “Ask one troubleshooting question per turn”), C is the detected troubleshooting category (e.g., network, database, application), H is the last five conversation turns to maintain context, and U is the latest user input.

This structured approach ensures that response optimization, discussed in the next section, builds upon the chatbot’s ability to dynamically adjust its troubleshooting depth based on prior responses.

C. Dynamic Response Optimization

The chatbot continuously refines its questioning strategy based on user responses and prior dialogue context. Unlike traditional static decision-tree models, our approach dynamically adjusts the diagnostic flow. This ensures that follow-up questions maximize information gain while maintaining an efficient troubleshooting structure. The optimization process carefully balances between in-depth questioning on a specific issue and broadening the scope to explore alternative failure points when necessary.

At each interaction step, the chatbot generates a follow-up question using an “iterative refinement process” rather than selecting from a precomputed set of candidate questions. The chatbot first constructs a prompt incorporating prior conversation history and uses the LLM to generate a response. However, due to the inherent variability in LLM outputs, the

generated response may sometimes be vague, redundant, or contain multiple questions within a single output. To mitigate these issues, the chatbot applies an internal refinement mechanism where it evaluates and regenerates the follow-up question up to ten times if the initial output does not meet quality criteria. While the chatbot asks a maximum of five user-facing questions, each question undergoes multiple internal refinement attempts before being presented. These refinements ensure that the question does not repeat previously gathered information, remains focused on a single aspect of the issue, and is contextually relevant. If the initial question is too broad or ambiguous, the chatbot generates an alternative that is more specific and actionable, ensuring that each question contributes effectively to the diagnostic process.

The chatbot dynamically determines whether to refine its focus on a specific issue or broaden the inquiry to explore alternative causes. If the user’s response provides substantial diagnostic insight, the chatbot continues probing within the same context. Conversely, if the response is inconclusive, the chatbot expands its inquiry to examine alternative hypotheses. This decision-making process is modeled as:

$$d_{\text{expand}} = \begin{cases} \text{Continue current path,} & \text{if } S_c(Q_{\text{new}}, H) > \theta_d \\ \text{Expand scope,} & \text{if } S_c(Q_{\text{new}}, H) \leq \theta_d \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where θ_d is an adaptive threshold that adjusts dynamically based on conversation depth and user responses. It decreases when responses are vague or contradictory, prompting broader inquiry, and increases when they align with a diagnostic category, reinforcing a focused approach. The function $S_c(Q_{\text{new}}, H)$ represents the contextual similarity score, which quantifies how well the newly generated question Q_{new} aligns with the historical conversation context H . A higher S_c value indicates that the new question remains relevant within the current diagnostic scope, while a lower S_c suggests that the chatbot should broaden its inquiry to explore alternative failure hypotheses.

To maintain a coherent and efficient diagnostic flow, the chatbot verifies that newly generated questions do not overlap with previous inquiries. This is achieved through a three-stage similarity filtering process:

First, lexical redundancy is detected using Jaccard similarity, which measures word overlap between the new and previous questions [8]:

$$J(Q_{\text{new}}, Q_{\text{prev}}) = \frac{|Q_{\text{new}} \cap Q_{\text{prev}}|}{|Q_{\text{new}} \cup Q_{\text{prev}}|} \quad (3)$$

If $J(Q_{\text{new}}, Q_{\text{prev}}) > 0.7$, the chatbot discards the generated question to avoid unnecessary repetition. The threshold value of 0.7 for Jaccard similarity was determined empirically by evaluating the chatbot’s performance across multiple test cases. Lower thresholds ($J < 0.6$) led to overly permissive filtering, allowing redundant rewordings, while higher values ($J > 0.8$) were too strict, discarding useful reformulations. Similar tuning was performed for Levenshtein distance ($L < 0.2$) and cosine similarity ($S_{\text{cosine}} > 0.8$) (discussed below), where we

adjusted the parameters based on observed chatbot behavior to balance redundancy filtering with question diversity.

Second, structural similarity filtering is applied using the Levenshtein (or edit) distance, which quantifies the minimum number of character insertions, deletions, or substitutions required to transform one question into another [9]:

$$L(Q_{\text{new}}, Q_{\text{prev}}) = \frac{D(Q_{\text{new}}, Q_{\text{prev}})}{\max(|Q_{\text{new}}|, |Q_{\text{prev}}|)} \quad (4)$$

where $D(Q_{\text{new}}, Q_{\text{prev}})$ represents the absolute edit distance. If $L(Q_{\text{new}}, Q_{\text{prev}}) < 0.2$, indicating only a minor rewording, the chatbot regenerates a more distinct follow-up.

Finally, to eliminate semantically redundant queries, sentence embeddings are compared using cosine similarity [10]:

$$S_{\text{cosine}}(Q_{\text{new}}, Q_{\text{prev}}) = \frac{Q_{\text{new}} \cdot Q_{\text{prev}}}{\|Q_{\text{new}}\| \cdot \|Q_{\text{prev}}\|} \quad (5)$$

If $S_{\text{cosine}} > 0.8$, the chatbot considers Q_{new} too similar to a previously asked question and generates an alternative.

Through this iterative refinement process, the chatbot systematically filters out redundant or ineffective queries, guaranteeing that each user-facing question contributes valuable new diagnostic information.

The chatbot terminates troubleshooting upon reaching the maximum depth of five structured follow-ups, achieving a pre-defined certainty threshold, or receiving an explicit termination request from the user. Upon termination, the chatbot generates a structured diagnostic report containing the issue classification, extracted symptoms, troubleshooting steps taken, and suggested next steps.

TABLE VI: Generated Trouble Ticket Structure

Field	Description
Issue Type	Categorized system misconfiguration
Key Symptoms	Extracted from conversation history
Troubleshooting Steps Taken	Follow-up questions asked
Suggested Next Steps	IT recommendations

D. Case Study: Diagnosing Network Misconfigurations

To illustrate the chatbot’s symptom collection process, consider a scenario where a user experiences an issue connecting to an enterprise database.

User Complaint: The user reports: “I am unable to connect to the database from my workstation, but my colleague can access it.”

Chatbot’s Structured Symptom Extraction Process:

1. *Initial classification:* The chatbot determines that this is likely a network-related issue.

2. *Dynamic inquiry generation:* Instead of presenting the user with generic troubleshooting steps, the chatbot asks targeted questions to gather relevant details, such as whether the issue is isolated to a single workstation, whether the colleague is on the same network, and whether there have been any recent authentication changes.

3. *Decision-based question refinement:* If the user confirms that other network services work, the chatbot focuses on

TABLE VII: Classification Accuracy Results

Metric	Value
Total Test Cases	75
Correct Classifications	73
Accuracy	97.33%

firewall settings or access control policies. If the user is on a different subnet from their colleague, the chatbot asks whether network segmentation rules are in place.

4. *Symptom extraction and handoff:* Once sufficient diagnostic information has been gathered, the chatbot compiles the extracted symptoms and passes them to the root cause analysis system.

E. Evaluation of Chatbot

The chatbot’s classification accuracy was evaluated using a benchmark test consisting of 75 predefined symptom sets, each mapped to a known issue category. The goal was to determine whether the chatbot could accurately classify reported issues based on extracted symptoms. The test covered four primary types of misconfigurations: application server failures, network issues, database server problems, and cases categorized as other when symptoms were ambiguous or did not match a specific failure domain.

Each test case presented a structured set of user-reported symptoms, and the chatbot was tasked with inferring the most likely issue type. The classification was then compared to the expected ground truth to assess accuracy. The primary evaluation metric was classification accuracy, which measures the proportion of correctly inferred issue types. Out of 75 test cases, the chatbot correctly classified 73, achieving an overall accuracy of 97.33% (Table VII).

To illustrate classification performance, Table VIII presents representative cases. While the majority were correctly identified, two cases were misclassified under “Other” instead of “Application Server”, suggesting that symptom ambiguity contributed to uncertainty in classification. Although these misclassifications did not prevent the chatbot from proceeding with relevant troubleshooting, they highlight areas where additional refinements could improve classification robustness.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The proposed approach enables intelligent fault categorization, real-time diagnosis, and streamlined remediation within enterprise environments. The chatbot’s high classification accuracy demonstrates its effectiveness in inferring misconfiguration types via a short dialog with the user. We also showed that the chatbot behaves well with respect to asking follow-up questions, avoiding repetition, keeping the dialog short, and handling of vague statements by the user.

One area of future research is the involvement of LLM in the diagnosis itself and its integration with the chatbot. Our enterprise network chatbot proposes a set of tests, which the analysis shows are quite relevant and in most cases the right ones for the diagnosis. However, we have yet to integrate this

TABLE VIII: Sample Test Cases and Classification Outcomes

Test Case	Symptoms	Expected Issue Type	Chatbot-Inferred Issue Type	Result
1	Website not loading, HTTP 500 error, Server logs indicate back-end failures	Application Server	Application Server	Correct
2	No internet access, Intermittent connectivity, All devices affected	Network Issue	Network Issue	Correct
3	Database queries are slow, Connection timeouts to MySQL, High CPU usage on DB server	Database Server	Database Server	Correct
7	Server is slow, High CPU usage, Increased response time	Application Server	Other	Mismatch
73	Web application load times increasing, No high CPU usage detected	Application Server	Other	Mismatch

capability with our diagnosis procedure. Other areas include enhancing the breadth of diagnosis procedures and ensuring that the chatbot can handle those aspects as well.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jez Humble and David Farley. *Continuous delivery: reliable software releases through build, test, and deployment automation*. Pearson Education, 2010.
- [2] Salman Baset, Sahil Suneja, Nilton Bila, Ozan Tuncer, and Canturk Isci. Usable declarative configuration specification and validation for applications, systems, and cloud. In *Proceedings of the 18th ACM/IFIP/USENIX Middleware Conference: Industrial Track*, pages 29–35, 2017.
- [3] Ching-Huang et al. Lin. A study and implementation of vulnerability assessment and misconfiguration detection. In *2008 IEEE Asia-Pacific Services Computing Conference*, pages 1252–1257. IEEE, 2008.
- [4] Negar Mohammadi Koushki, Ibrahim El-Shekeil, and Krishna Kant. Confexp: Root-cause analysis of service misconfigurations in enterprise systems. *Journal of Network and Systems Management*, 33(2):1–31, 2025.
- [5] Gartner. Gartner Identifies the Top Cybersecurity Trends for 2023, 2023. Accessed: 2025-03-07.
- [6] Palo Alto Networks. Critical Cloud Misconfigurations in AWS, 2019. Accessed: 2025-03-07.
- [7] Albert Q. Jiang, Alexandre Sablayrolles, Arthur Mensch, et al. Mistral 7b. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2310.06825, 2023.
- [8] Sujoy Bag, Sri Krishna Kumar, and Manoj Kumar Tiwari. An efficient recommendation generation using relevant jaccard similarity. *Information Sciences*, 483:53–64, 2019.
- [9] Li Yujian and Liu Bo. A normalized levenshtein distance metric. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 29(6):1091–1095, 2007.
- [10] Peipei Xia, Li Zhang, and Fanzhang Li. Learning similarity with cosine similarity ensemble. *Information sciences*, 307:39–52, 2015.

APPENDIX

A. Mistral LLM:

Mistral 7B, a LLM with 7 billion parameters, serves as the backbone of the chatbot’s conversational capabilities. Pre-trained on a diverse corpus of text, Mistral 7B excels at generating contextually relevant and coherent responses, making it ideal for handling open-ended and ambiguous user

inputs. The model’s ability to maintain context across multi-turn conversations is particularly valuable in fault diagnosis scenarios, where users often provide incomplete or vague descriptions of their issues.

The probability of generating a response R given a user input U and conversation history H is modeled as:

$$P(R|U, H) = \prod_{t=1}^T P(w_t|w_{<t}, U, H)$$

where w_t is the t -th token in the response, and T is the total number of tokens. This autoregressive formulation allows the model to generate responses token-by-token, ensuring fluency and coherence.

To adapt Mistral 7B for fault diagnosis, the model is fine-tuned on a domain-specific dataset containing user-chatbot interactions. The fine-tuning objective minimizes the negative log-likelihood:

$$\mathcal{L} = - \sum_{t=1}^T \log P(w_t|w_{<t}, U, H)$$

The dataset includes 275 labeled examples across 8 fault types as instruction-output pairs. It is augmented with synthetic data for vague reports. Fine-tuning is performed using LoRA (Low-Rank Adaptation), a parameter-efficient method that updates only a small subset of the model’s weights. LoRA introduces low-rank matrices A and B to approximate weight updates ΔW :

$$\Delta W = A \cdot B$$

where $A \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r}$ and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times k}$ are low-rank matrices with rank $r \ll d, k$. This reduces the number of trainable parameters while preserving model performance. For the tuning process, the batch size, epochs and ranks were set to 8, 3 and 8 respectively.

B. BERT Model

BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) is employed for intent classification, mapping user inputs to specific fault types. BERT’s bidirectional attention mechanism enables it to capture contextual relationships between words, making it highly effective for understanding user complaints. The steps involved in Intent Classification are: a) *Tokenization*: The user input is tokenized into subword tokens using the DistilBERT tokenizer, b) *Embedding*: The tokenized input is passed through BERT to obtain contextualized embeddings and c) *Classification*: The [CLS] token

embedding is used to compute the probability distribution over fault types. Two variants of BERT are experimented with: pre-trained BERT for zero-shot classification and fine-tuned BERT for improved accuracy.

For an input sequence $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, BERT computes contextualized embeddings h_i for each token. The [CLS] token embedding $h_{[\text{CLS}]}$ is used for classification:

$$P(y|X) = \text{softmax}(W \cdot h_{[\text{CLS}]} + b)$$

where W and b are learnable parameters.

1) *Fine-Tuning BERT*: The model is fine-tuned using **cross-entropy loss**:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log P(y_i|X_i)$$

Training is performed for 2 epochs with a batch size of 16 and weight decay of 0.01. The optimizer used is AdamW, which combines the benefits of Adam optimization with weight decay regularization.

C. Dataset Augmentation

Data augmentation is a technique used to increase the diversity and size of the training dataset, improving the model's ability to generalize to unseen data. One approach to data augmentation is back-translation, where a text is translated into another language and then translated back into English. For example, the original sentence "App won't open at all." can be translated into French as "L'application ne s'ouvre pas du tout." and then back into English as "The application does not open at all." A technique that has been implemented for this experimentation is synonym replacement, where words are substituted with their synonyms. For instance, "Loading takes forever." can be augmented to "Loading takes an eternity." Noise injection is another method that has been used. It involves introducing minor typos or grammatical errors to simulate real-world user inputs. An example is modifying "I can't access my account." to "I cant access my account." Additionally, paraphrasing can be used to rewrite a sentence while preserving its meaning. For example, "The website says connection failed." can be transformed into "The website indicates that the connection has failed." The impact of data augmentation is significant. It leads to improved generalization, allowing the model to better handle unseen inputs. It enhances robustness, making the model more resilient to variations in phrasing and linguistic styles.